

Isolation and identification of phenol removing bacteria from contaminated soil of industrial effluent

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Abstract : The toxicity of phenol has been widely documented and their disastrous effect towards human and environment is greatly concerned. It causes negative effects to aquatic flora and fauna. The present investigation has been undertaken to isolate and identify the microbes capable of removing phenol from the effluents of Dankuni Coal Complex. Soil sample containing high phenol/phenolic compounds were collected from the effluent of Dankuni Coal Complex. The strains were isolated from these soil samples by selective enrichment culture in MS medium. The morphology and gram character of the strains were determined by gram staining and the organisms were then identified according to protocols followed by Bergey's Manual of systematic bacteriology. Two bacterial strains were isolated which could tolerate phenol of different concentrations to the extent of 1000 ppm and 3000 ppm. By performing 16s ribotyping the strains were characterized. Out of the two strains, one strain which could withstand phenol up to 3000 ppm was found to be *Staphylococcus sciuri* strain SCH1JF914984 and the other strain which could tolerate a phenol concentration of 1000 ppm was found to be *Bacillus pumilus* strain SCH2JF914985.

The main significance of the study is the utilization of native bacterial strains from the industrial waste itself having potential of bioremediation.

Keywords : Phenol, 16s ribotyping, *Staphylococcus sciuri* strain SCH1JF914984, *Bacillus pumilus* strain SCH2JF914985.

Introduction

Phenolics constitute 11 of the 126 chemicals that have been designated as priority pollutants by the United States Environmental Protection Agency¹. The Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) calls for lowering phenol content in the wastewater to less than 1 mg/L. Phenols are common starting materials and often waste byproducts in the manufacture of industrial and agricultural products. Especially phenolic compounds are often found in wastewaters from coal gasification, coke-oven batteries, refinery and petrochemical plants and other industries, such as synthetic chemicals, herbicides, pesticides, antioxidants, pulp-and-paper, photo developing chemicals, etc.². Now the associated problem due to phenol is that when it is present in wastewater even in low concentrations, it can be toxic to some aquatic species and causes taste and odour problems in drinking water³. Inhalation and der-

mal contact of phenol causes cardiovascular diseases and severe skin damage, while ingestion can cause serious gastrointestinal damage and oral administration into laboratory animals has also induced muscle tremors and death. Phenols, even at low concentration are very toxic to unicellular and multicellular cells. Therefore, the removal of such chemicals from industrial effluents is of great importance. Biological treatment, activated carbon adsorption, solvent extraction, chemical oxidation and electrochemical methods are the most widely used methods for removing phenol and phenolic compounds from wastewaters⁴. Problems such as high cost, low efficiency and generation of toxic by-products are limiting factors for wide applications of some of these remediation strategies.

Degradation of phenol occurs as a result of the activity of a large number of microorganisms including bac-

teria, fungi and actinomycetes. However, these microorganisms suffer from substrate inhibition at higher concentration of phenol, by which the growth is inhibited.

Biodegradation has been studied as an alternative approach due to the low costs associated with this option, as well as the possibility of complete dissolution of the xenobiotic⁵. Phenol biodegradation has been studied in detail using pure and mixed cultures of suspended bacteria⁶.

In our experiments, the cells have been isolated from industrial effluents and subsequently acclimatized with higher concentrations of phenol. The objective of the present study is to isolate organisms that can tolerate high level of phenol and characterization of the isolated organisms.

Materials and methods :

Growth media :

A basic mineral salts medium (MS medium) was used for the isolation of the organisms. Bacteria were grown on a MS medium⁷ containing (per liter) 2.75 g K₂HPO₄, 2.25 g KH₂PO₄, 1 g (NH₄)₂SO₄, 0.2 g MgCl₂.6H₂O, 0.1 g NaCl, 0.02 g FeCl₃.6H₂O and 0.01 g CaCl₂ at pH 7. Phenol (GR, 99.5%, Merck) were added to this medium in different concentrations (ranging from 10 ppm to 3100 ppm), where phenol acted as a carbon source for the bacterium. Phenol was dissolved in distilled water and added to 250 ml Erlenmeyer flask containing 100 ml of Mineral Salt Medium.

Isolation of strain :

Phenol-utilizing bacteria were isolated from samples taken from Dankuni Coal Complex. Samples (1 g of soil sample) was suspended in 10 ml of sterile distilled water. 1 ml of this culture was suspended in 9 ml of sterile distilled water and marked as a stock solution. Isolated colonies were obtained by serial dilution of the stock and plating them on medium containing different concentrations of phenol. The organisms were also grown in mineral salt broth with different phenol concentration under agitation condition (150 rpm). The bacteria were grown on these media under aerobic condition at 37 °C in a shaker in case of liquid culture and aerobically in an incubator at 37 °C in case of agar culture. Out of 12 different colonies two different strains were considered which were able to withstand high amount of phenol, strain SCH(1) could withstand 3000 ppm and strain SCH(2)

could withstand 1000 ppm of phenol.

Identification of isolates :

The isolates were identified based on morphological observations and biochemical characterization. For morphological observation both the strains were grown in Mineral salt agar medium containing upto 1000 ppm and 3000 ppm phenol concentration. pH was maintained at 7 and the plates were incubated at 37 °C for 48 h. Different biochemical tests such as gram staining, spore staining, motility test, carbohydrate fermentation test, catalase reaction were performed with the isolated strains⁸. Bergey's manual of determinative bacteriology was used as a reference to identify the isolates. Then PCR amplification of 16s rRNA genes (16s rDNA) using consensus bacterial primers were performed.

Isolation of genomic DNA :

DNA was isolated from the two strains by using Himedia's HiPurA Bacterial and yeast Genomic DNA Miniprep Purification Spin kit. Bacterial cells were grown in a medium till they reached log phase and were harvested by centrifugation. After harvesting, the bacterial cell wall was degraded by lysozyme and Proteinase K. Following lysis, the DNA was bound to the silica-gel membrane of the HiElute Miniprep Spin Column to yield pure DNA. DNA concentrations were estimated by visual examination of ethidium bromide-stained agarose gels as well as by spectrophotometrical examination.

Amplification of 16s rDNA :

Partial amplification of the 16s rRNA gene was performed with the thermal cycler ABI 9700 (ABI, Foster City, USA). The PCR of the genomic DNA of the 2 strains were conducted in a final volume of 50 µL. The reaction mixture included 20–50 ng of isolated genomic DNA, 2U taq polymerase (Vivantis, India), 1 x PCR buffer with 1.5 mM MgCl₂, 200 µM each dNTP and 10 pmol of each primer (Patel De Chem, India). The primers were chosen to amplify an 875-bp segment of 16s rDNA. The forward primer used 515F was (5'–3') GTGCCAGCAGCCGCGGTAA and the reverse primer 1492R was (5'–3') TACGGYTACCTTGTTACGACTT⁹. Before amplification cycle DNA was denatured for 2 min at 94 °C and after amplification an extension step (7 min at 72 °C) was performed. The cycling parameters consisted of 28 cycles : denaturation at 94 °C for 30 s, primer annealing at 45 °C for 1 min, extension at 72 °C

for 1 min. The samples were held at 4 °C until analysis by agarose gel electrophoresis. All the amplified PCR products were agarose-gel-eluted using Himedia's HiPurA Agarose gel DNA Purification spin kit. Then the eluted products were sent for sequencing, which was done by MWG-BIOTECH Pvt. Ltd., Sequencing Department, India.

Accession number :

The sequences were submitted to Gene Bank and accession numbers were assigned : SCH (1) JF914984 and SCH (2) JF914985.

Then the 16s rDNA sequence was blast searched against gene bank database. Identification to the species level was determined as a 16s rDNA sequence similarity of 100% and 99% with that of the prototype strain sequence in the Gene Bank.

Results and discussion

In the present study twelve different isolates were obtained from the effluent, but only two major colonies were selected for identification and they were identified based on morphological, cultural, biochemical characteristics and molecular approach (16s rRNA analysis). Out of the two strains strain SCH1 can withstand a phenol concentration of 3000 ppm and strain SCH2 can withstand a concentration of 1000 ppm phenol. Their morphological, colonial, biochemical characteristics and their ability for carbohydrate fermentation are given in Table 1 and Table 2 respectively. The results showed that strain SCH1 is Gram-positive cocci found singly and in cluster

Table 1. Morphological and colony characteristics of bacterial strains able to grow on medium containing phenol

Experiment	Observation of strain SCH1	Observation of strain SCH2
Morphology	Spherical	Rods
Arrangement	Single, clustered	Single, double, clustered
Gram stain	Positive	Positive
Spore stain	Negative	Positive
Motility	Negative	Positive
Opacity	Opaque	Mucoid
Surface growth	Smooth	Smooth
Edge	Entire	Irregular
Consistency	Good	Good
Colour	White	Yellowish white
Pigment	Nil	Nil

Table 2. Biochemical characteristics

Parameters	Observation for strain SCH1	Observation for strain SCH2
Indole test	-ve	-ve
Methyl red test	+ve	-ve
VP test	+ve	-ve
Citrate utilization test	+ve	+ve
Urease activity	+ve	-ve
Catalase test	+ve	+ve
Oxidase test	-ve	-ve
Starch hydrolysis	-ve	+ve
Growth at anaerobic condition	-ve	-ve
Carbohydrate fermentation (gas production)		
Fructose	-ve	-ve
Arabinose	-ve	-ve
Galactose	-ve	-ve
Xylose	-ve	-ve
Glucose	-ve	-ve
Lactose	-ve	-ve
Sucrose	-ve	-ve
Maltose	-ve	-ve
Raffinose	-ve	-ve
Acid production		
Fructose	+ve	-ve
Arabinose	+ve	-ve
Galactose	+ve	-ve
Xylose	+ve	-ve
Glucose	+ve	-ve
Lactose	+ve	-ve
Sucrose	+ve	-ve
Maltose	+ve	-ve
Raffinose	+ve	-ve

and strain SCH2 is Gram-positive rod. Both the strains showed negative result for Indole test. Strain SCH1 showed positive results for methyl red, citrate utilization and catalase test. Strain SCH2 showed negative results for indole, methyl red and urease activity, it was positive for citrate utilization and Catalase test. Strain SCH1 could ferment carbohydrate with the production of acidic end products whereas strain SCH2 was non carbohydrate fermenter.

Analyses of 16s rRNA gene :

The 16s rRNA gene sequences of both the species were submitted at Gene Bank under Accession No.

JF914984 and JF914985. Comparison with available sequences in Gene Bank showed very high similarity of organism JF914985 (SCH2) with *Bacillus pumilus* and JF914984 (SCH1) with *Staphylococcus sciuri*. Phylogenetic tree of both the strains based on known representatives of related species are presented in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2.

Conclusion :

In the present study two strains have been isolated from the phenol contaminated soil which can tolerate high concentration of phenol. After performing various biochemical tests, 16s RNA analysis was conducted. The results obtained from the analysis of the partial sequence

of the two bacterial strains, isolated from the phenol contaminated site showed that *Staphylococcus sciuri* strain SCH1JF914984 can withstand a concentration of 3000 ppm although most other organisms show substrate inhibition at such high concentration. The other strain was identified as *Bacillus pumilus* strain SCH2 JF914985 and could withstand a concentration of 1000 ppm. Morphologically *Staphylococcus sciuri* colonies are large circular, smooth, opaque whereas *Bacillus pumilus* is raised, mucoid, dull, yellowish white colonies. *S. sciuri* is non-motile and *B. pumilus* is motile. *Bacillus pumilus* and *Staphylococcus sciuri* tested positive for citrate utilization.

Fig. 1. Dendrogram illustrating the (16s rDNA gene) similarity of the bacteria JF914985 to strains exhibiting highest sequence similarity.

Fig. 2. Dendrogram illustrating the (16s rDNA gene) similarity of the bacteria JF914984 to strains exhibiting highest sequence similarity.

tion. For Methyl red and Voges poskeur test, *Bacillus pumilus* showed negative result and *Staphylococcus sciuri* showed positive result. Both the strains showed positive results for Catalase test and starch hydrolysis test. Also both *S. sciuri* and *B. pumilus* could not grow in anaerobic conditions. The current investigation was aimed at understanding the types of microorganisms found in phenol contaminated soils by their proper identification. Both *Staphylococcus sciuri* strain SCH1 JF914984 and *Bacillus pumilus* strain SCH2 JF914985 are novel strains to be studied in this field. Further investigations are being carried out to determine the removal efficiency of both the strains and if possible to improve their removal efficiency by mutating the organisms.

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